

**INFLUENCE OF HOT-SPOT ON CRACK PATH AND LIFETIME ESTIMATION OF
FRETTING-AFFECTED STEEL COMPONENTS**

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ABSTRACT

The crack nucleation orientation of fretting-affected components made of AISI1034 steel and 35NCD16 steel is analysed in the

present paper. In particular, both cylinder-to-flat and sphere-to-flat contact configurations in partial slip regime are simulated by means of an analytical methodology based on elastic assumptions. Different crack nucleation locations on the contact surface are considered in order to estimate both the crack nucleation orientation and the lifetime. Satisfactory results are obtained by employing such a methodology, especially when both the stress state within the specimen and the relative slip between the specimen and the pad are taken into account in the fretting assessment procedure.

KEYWORDS

35NCD16 steel, AISI1034 steel, analytical methodology, crack nucleation location, critical plane, Ruiz parameter.

1. INTRODUCTION

In last decades, several catastrophic events have been attributed to the rupture of metallic structural components due to fretting [1]. Among such components it is possible to mention for instance dovetail joints, bolt and riveted joints, spline coupling, running cables and overhead conductors [2-5]. Such failures may occur when structural components in contact to each other experience vibrations or small relative oscillatory movements.

A typical damage mechanism can be observed in fretting-affected components [6]. The initial phase consists in the scarring of the

superficial oxide layer and in the subsequent formation of cold-welds at the surface asperities. As a consequence, the friction coefficient between the contact surfaces changes and, in particular, it has experimentally been observed to increase during the first few hundreds of loading cycles [7]. Subsequently, due to the breaking of the above micro-welds, micro-debris appear between the contact surfaces. Such debris initially promote further abrasion of the material, thus resulting in the formation of a protective layer which reduces the wear of the material itself.

As the number of loading cycles increases, several grain-sized micro-cracks nucleates in the vicinity of the contact zone, due to localised plastic deformations [8]. In such a condition, the propagation of the above micro-cracks into the bulk material may be promoted by a tensile (either static or cyclic) remote loading experienced by the structural components, thus leading to their final rupture [9].

The crack nucleation mechanism is governed by the high stress gradients expected in the vicinity of the contact zone due to the fretting phenomenon, and strongly depends on the material microstructure [10,11]. On the other hand, the crack propagation mechanism is related to the remote loading [7]. It is widely accepted by the scientific community that crack nucleation represents the main mechanism, involving the major part (around 90%) of the total life of the fretting-affected components, whereas only a small amount of the total life is related to crack

propagation [12]. Therefore, a crack-nucleation approach may be applied in order to assess the fretting fatigue behaviour of metallic structural components.

Most fretting-related failures occur in high-cycle fatigue regime conditions and are characterised by a multi-axial stress state. Moreover, the situation in which only part of the contact surface experiences micro-slips (named *partial slip regime*) is considered much more dangerous than the case of total sliding between the bodies in contact (named *gross slip regime*). In fact, partial slip regime is generally characterised by more severe stress gradients, which may be up to ten times higher than those occurring in metallic notched components [13].

Many efforts have been made in the past in order to analyse the mechanics of fretting problems, as well as to define methodologies for fretting fatigue assessment. In particular, in order to properly take into account the severe stress gradients, Amargier et al. [14] proposed a methodology, based on the assumption of a decreasing linear function, for numerically computing the stress state around the hot-spot. Accurate results have been obtained by employing this technique, but at the expense of very high computational costs of the finite element numerical model.

Moreover, Montebello et al. [15] introduced an alternative technique based on fracture mechanics. In particular, they combined non-local stress intensity factors in order to simulate the crack nucleation mechanism. This methodology also provided

very promising estimations, but it is still based on complex numerical computations.

In order to overcome the complexity of the above two techniques, either analytical or simple numerical models may be employed in conjunction with non-local approaches in order to consider the presence of the near surface stress gradients. In such a context, both stress averaging methods and methods based on the Theory of the Critical Distance are commonly applied to take into account the stress gradient effect [16-19].

Furthermore, methodologies based on the stress/strain field within the fretting-affected component are able to provide satisfactory estimations in terms of fatigue life [20-26]. However, it has become recently evident that such methodologies are not accurate in predicting the fretting crack nucleation mechanism, that is crack nucleation location and orientation [27].

In such a context, a critical plane-based analytical methodology [28-32], recently proposed by some of the present authors, is here applied for the fretting fatigue assessment of metallic specimens subjected to fretting fatigue in partial slip regime. Such a methodology is based on the joint use of: (i) a closed-form solution [7,33,34] for the stress/strain field determination, based on the Hertzian theory for contact between elastic bodies, (ii) a multiaxial fatigue criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37] for the fatigue assessment, and (iii) a stress averaging method, named Critical Direction Method (CDM) [38,39], to determine the orientation of the critical

plane. Moreover, this methodology takes into account a parameter related to the material microstructure, that is, the average grain size of the material.

In the last few years, such a methodology has been applied to different materials, fretting loading and contact configurations. According to its original formulation, the crack is assumed to nucleate at the edge of the contact, based on considerations related to the stress field within the material. However, cracks nucleating in points other than the contact edge, within the slip region, have been experimentally observed in the literature **[40,41]**.

Therefore, in the present paper different crack nucleation locations (starting from the contact edge and moving inside the contact surface) are considered in order to analyse the influence of such a location on fatigue assessment, in terms of both crack path orientation and lifetime. More precisely, different points within the micro-slip zone are alternatively assumed as crack nucleation location, and the methodology is applied for each of such locations. Note that, the Ruiz parameter **[2]** is considered in order to define one of such points, to correlate the crack nucleation location to both the stress state within the material and the micro-slips at interface between the components.

Three different experimental campaigns available in the literature are analysed, that is: cylindrical fretting tests on AISI1034 steel specimens **[42]**, cylindrical fretting tests on 35NCD16 steel specimens **[43]**, and spherical fretting tests on

35NCD16 steel specimens [43]. The results obtained by means of the abovementioned analytical methodology, for each experimental campaign and by considering different crack nucleation locations, are compared with the experimental findings in terms of both crack nucleation location and orientation, and fatigue life.

The present paper is structured as follows. **Section 2** deals with the description of the experimental campaigns analysed and available in the literature [42,43]. Then, **Section 3** is devoted to describe the analytical methodology [28-32] employed for such simulations (note that the theoretical aspects on which the methodology is based are outlined in **Appendix A**). The results obtained are reported and discussed in **Section 4**, and conclusions are summarised in **Section 5**.

2. EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGNS ANALYSED

In the present Section, a brief description of the experimental campaigns analysed is provided, and in particular:

- experimental tests available in the literature [42] and carried out on AISI 1034 steel under *cylindrical contact* are presented in Sub-Section 2.1;
- experimental tests available in the literature [43] and carried out on 35NCD16 steel alloy under *cylindrical contact* are presented in Sub-Section 2.2;

- experimental tests available in the literature [43] and carried out on 35NCD16 steel alloy under *spherical contact* are presented in Sub-Section 2.3.

2.1 Experimental campaign No. 1: AISI 1034 steel subjected to cylindrical contact

The experimental campaign carried out by Fouvry et al. [42] on AISI 1034 carbon steel specimens is hereafter described. The medium carbon steel employed is characterised by a carbon content between 0.31 and 0.55 by weight and high mechanical properties (both mechanical and fatigue properties of AISI 1034 are listed in **Table 1** [42,44]). The major applications of this material are levers, bolts and nuts, air compressors, pistons, heavy machinery shafts, gears, crankshafts and other structural components where moving parts are needed.

Table 1.

Fretting tests in partial slip regime were performed by employing a fretting device rigidly mounted onto a servo hydraulic testing machine, able to reproduce a cylinder-to-flat contact configuration. The pad radius, R , was equal to 40 mm and its length was 5 mm, promoting plane strain conditions near the central axis of the fretting contact zone. Chromium 52100 steel (whose mechanical properties are listed in **Table 1** [42]) was used

for the pad, in order to both have elastically similar bodies in contact and ensure the nucleation of cracks in the specimen only.

An average grain size, d , equal to 30 microns was found for the AISI 1034 steel and a friction coefficient, μ , equal to 0.9 was determined between the two materials employed [42].

The pad was pushed against the specimen by means of a constant normal load P and, subsequently, a cyclic tangential load $Q(t)$, with an amplitude equal to Q_a , was applied to the pad, with a loading ratio equal to -1 and a frequency equal to 40 Hz (see **Figure 1(a)**). Two different loading configurations (named R1 and R2 in the following) were considered. The values of the constant normal load and the tangential load amplitude are listed in **Table 2** for each loading configuration, together with the theoretical semi-widths of both the contact zone a (see Eq. (A.2)) and the stick zone c (see Eq. (A.10)).

Figure 1.

Table 2.

The tests were stopped at 10^6 fretting cycles in order to analyse the experimental crack paths. The cracks were generally observed to nucleate in the proximity of the contact trailing edge, but no detailed information regarding the crack nucleation location is available in Ref. [42]. Such cracks were characterised by an average orientation α_{exp} (defined from the line perpendicular to the surface of the component, with positive

values if the crack is towards the centre of the contact zone) equal to 30° and 22.7° , for loading configuration R1 and R2, respectively. Such values were measured when the crack length was equal to about 50 microns and 55 microns, respectively.

2.2 Experimental campaign No. 2: 35NCD16 steel subjected to cylindrical contact

The experimental campaign carried out by Baietto et al. [43] on 35NCD16 alloy steel specimens is hereafter described. The material employed is characterised by very high strengths together with good fracture behaviour and wear resistance (both mechanical and fatigue properties of 35NCD16 are listed in **Table 3 [43,45]**). The major applications of this material are shafts, torsion shafts, axles, levers, connecting rods, rocker arms and other structural components subjected to very high stress field and characterised by large section or complex shape.

Table 3.

Fretting tests in partial slip regime were performed by employing a fretting device rigidly mounted onto a servo hydraulic testing machine, able to reproduce a cylinder-to-flat contact configuration. The pad radius, R , was equal to 80 mm and its length was 8 mm, promoting plane strain conditions near the central axis of the fretting contact zone. Heat treated steel 100 C6 (whose mechanical properties are listed in **Table 3 [43]**) was

used for the pad, in order to both have elastically similar bodies in contact and ensure the nucleation of cracks in the specimen only.

An average grain size, d , equal to 15 microns was found for the 35NCD16 alloy steel [46] and a friction coefficient, μ , equal to 0.9 was determined between the two materials employed [43].

When present, a constant tensile bulk load, σ_B , was first applied to the specimen in order to avoid the off-set of the stick zones during the test. Subsequently, after the pad was pushed against the specimen by means of a constant normal load P , a cyclic tangential load $Q(t)$ was applied to the pad, with a loading ratio equal to -1 and a frequency equal to 13 Hz (see **Figure 1(b)**). Five different loading configurations (named T1-T5 in the following) were considered. The values of the constant normal load, the tangential load amplitude and the constant bulk stress are listed in **Table 4** for each loading configuration, together with the theoretical semi-widths of both the contact zone a (see Eq. (A.2)) and the stick zone c (see Eq. (A.10)).

Table 4.

The tests were stopped at a number of fretting cycles between $5 \cdot 10^5$ and 10^6 in order to analyse the experimental crack paths. The cracks were generally observed to nucleate inside the contact zone, close to the contact trailing edge, that is within the slip zone. Such cracks were characterised by an average orientation

α_{exp} equal to 15.7° , measured when the crack length was equal to about 30 microns.

2.3 Experimental campaign No. 3: 35NCD16 steel subjected to spherical contact

The experimental campaign carried out by Baietto et al. [43] on 35NCD16 alloy steel specimens is hereafter described. The materials employed, for both specimen and pad, are the same as those of the experimental campaign No. 2 described in Sub-Section 2.2 (see **Table 3**).

Fretting tests in partial slip regime were performed by employing a fretting device rigidly mounted onto a servo hydraulic testing machine, able to reproduce a sphere-to-flat contact configuration. The pad radius, R , was equal to 200 mm.

The pad was pushed against the specimen by means of a constant normal load P and, subsequently, a cyclic tangential load $Q(t)$ was applied to the pad, with a loading ratio equal to -1 and a frequency equal to 13 Hz (see **Figure 1(a)**). The values of the constant normal load and the tangential load amplitude are listed in **Table 5** for the loading configuration considered, together with the theoretical semi-widths of both the contact zone a (see Eq. (A.5)) and the stick zone c (see Eq. (A.12)).

Table 5.

The tests were stopped at $7.5 \cdot 10^5$ fretting cycles in order to analyse the experimental crack paths. The cracks, which nucleated within the slip zone, were characterised by an average orientation α_{exp} equal to 14.3° , measured when the crack length was equal to 30 microns.

3. ANALITICAL METHODOLOGY EMPLOYED

This Section deals with the description of the main steps of the analytical methodology proposed by the present authors for the fretting assessment of metallic structures, subjected to either cylindrical or spherical contact, in partial slip regime [28-32].

Such a methodology is based on:

- (i) a closed-form solution [7,33,34] for the stress/strain field determination within elastic bodies in contact (see Section A.1 of the Appendix A);
- (ii) a multiaxial fatigue criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37], for the fatigue parameter computation (see Section A.2 of the Appendix A);
- (iii) a stress averaging method, named Critical Direction Method [38,39], for the determination of the orientation of the critical plane (see Section A.3 of the Appendix A).

Moreover, this methodology takes into account a parameter related to the material microstructure, that is, the average grain size of the material, d .

Firstly, some *input data* need to be defined, that is: the geometric sizes and the loading conditions characterising the contact problem, and the mechanical and fatigue properties of the materials of the bodies involved.

Then, the *stress state* within the structural component is computed, and the *hot-spot* (that is, the point on the material surface where the crack is assumed to nucleate) is defined on the surface of the component itself.

Successively, the *critical plane orientation* is determined according to the procedure hereafter detailed, with reference to **Figure 2**. In particular, material planes passing through the hot-spot and characterised by different orientations α (measured with respect to the line perpendicular to the surface of the component, being its value positive if the crack is towards the centre of the contact zone) are considered. Initially, an orientation equal to zero is assumed (first critical plane candidate). Then, the stress components acting on the corresponding plane are computed in different equally spaced points, from the hot-spot and moving inside the material along the plane itself, up to a length equal to twice the average grain size of the material, $2d$. Such stress components, averaged along the critical plane candidate, are employed for the computation of the fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, related to the considered orientation, and defined in accordance with the Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37] (see Eq. (A.14)). Then a new orientation is taken into account (that is, another critical plane candidate is considered), and the procedure is

iterated for all material planes inward the component. The orientation, α_{cr} , that produces the maximum value of the above fatigue parameter is referred to as the critical plane.

Consequently, the *theoretical crack orientation*, α_{th} , is determined, being such an orientation assumed coincident to α_{cr} (that is, the critical plane orientation).

Finally, the *fatigue life*, $N_{f,cal}$, of the component analysed is computed according to the Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37], (see Eq. (A.13)), by employing the stress components acting on the critical plane at the verification point, S_{cr} , which is located on the critical plane at a distance from the hot-spot equal to twice the average grain size of the material, $2d$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental campaigns, available in the literature [42,43] and described in Section 2, are here analysed through the analytical methodology recently proposed by some of the present authors [28-32] and summarized in Section 3. Different hot-spots are assumed on the contact surface for each experimental campaign, in order to analyse the influence of the crack nucleation location on the fatigue assessment in terms of both crack path orientation and lifetime. More in detail, in accordance to experimental evidences of cracks nucleating within the slip region, four hot-spots are hereafter examined, that is (**Figure 3**):

- *point A*, characterised by the maximum value of the maximum principal stress expected within a fretting cycle, and located at the trailing edge of the contact (that is, $x=a$ in **Figure 3**);
- *point B*, characterised by the maximum value of the Ruiz parameter k [2] expected within a fretting cycle, and generally located within the slip zone close to the trailing edge of the contact (that is, $c < x \leq a$ in **Figure 3**). Note that the Ruiz parameter is defined as a function of both the normal and shear stresses acting parallel to the material surface, and the amplitude of the relative micro-slip between the bodies in contact;
- *point C*, located in the centre of the slip zone (that is, $x=(c+a)/2$ in **Figure 3**);
- *point D*, located at the boundary between the slip zone and the stick zone (that is, $x=c$ in **Figure 3**).

Figure 3.

It is worth noticing that points C and D are not representative of the physics of the fretting problem, since they are not related to the stress field within the component, neither to the relative slip conditions at the contact interface. On the other hand, point A is related to the stress field within the component, but it does not take into account the relative slip conditions at the contact interface. Moreover, point B is related to both the

stress field within the component and the relative slip conditions at the contact interface.

The fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}$, employed for the computation of the critical plane orientation is plotted in **Figures 4-7** for each loading configuration examined, as a function of the angle of the critical plane candidate. It is worth noticing that, as the hot-spot moves from point A to point D, the maximum value of the fatigue parameter decreases, whereas the corresponding angle (that is, the critical plane orientation) increases, and this holds true for all the loading configurations. This is the result of the very high stress gradient in the vicinity of the contact surface, and the stress concentration at the edge of the contact.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

The estimated values of crack nucleation orientation, $\alpha_{th,i}$ ($i=A,B,C,D$), are listed in **Table 6** for each loading configuration considered. It can be noted that all the orientations obtained are towards the centre of the contact region, in accordance to the experimental observations. Moreover, as the hot-spot moves inward the contact region (that is, from point A to point D), the estimated values of crack orientation increase, with values between 1° and 9° at point A, between 14°

and 18° at point B, between 21° and 29° at point C, and between 37° and 76° at point D. As far as the experimental campaign No. 3 is considered, a crack almost perpendicular to the surface is estimated in point A, whereas a particularly high value of α_{th} is obtained in point D. These results, quite different from those related to the other experimental campaigns, are probably related to the nature of the contact, that is sphere-to-flat, which is characterised by a more severe variation of the fretting conditions within the contact zone.

Table 6.

The crack nucleation orientation estimated by means of the present methodology, by taking into account the above four crack nucleation locations, are graphically reported in **Figure 8** for one loading configuration of each experimental campaign examined. The experimental crack paths (see the black lines in **Figure 8**) are also shown for comparison.

Figure 8.

It is possible to note that the results obtained by considering the hot-spot in point B or C are able to fit the experimental observations better than those in points A and D in terms of crack orientation. On the other hand, point A and B are more representative of the actual crack nucleation location, since in general it appears to be within the slip zone between such points.

Therefore, it seems that point B represents the best hot-spot location in order to achieve the most accurate correlation between theoretical estimations and experimental evidences in terms of both crack nucleation location and orientation.

Finally, the number of loading cycles to failure, $N_{f,cal}$, evaluated by assuming points A, B, C, and D as hot-spots, is shown in **Figure 9** for each loading configuration examined, where the dashed lines represent the number of loading cycles in correspondence of which the tests were stopped, N_{exp} .

Figure 9.

As the crack nucleation location moves inward the contact region (that is, from point A to point D), the estimated values of $N_{f,cal}$ generally increase. Moreover, when point A is assumed as the hot-spot, the values obtained are slightly lower or slightly higher than N_{exp} , whereas values higher than N_{exp} are obtained when the other points are considered. However, a detailed discussion in terms of fatigue life is not possible for the present case, since no data related to the experimental number of loading cycles to failure are available in Refs. **[42,43]**.

It is important to highlight that the methodology here employed is based on elastic behaviour assumption. Accordingly, in order to verify the applicability of such a methodology, the Hertzian rule may be considered. In particular, if the ratio between the maximum value of the contact pressure (computed according to Eqs.

A.3 and A.6) and the material yield stress is below 1.6, an elastic stress/strain field may be assumed, whereas if a higher value is obtained, plastic deformations are expected.

For the experimental campaigns here examined, an elastic behaviour is expected for all the loading configurations, except for loading configuration R2, for which the above ratio is equal to 1.99. In such a case, plastic deformations are expected in a narrow area close to the surface, due to the partial slip conditions. Consequently, a purely elastic methodology, such as that used here, would overestimate the stress field.

Therefore, the use of the present elastic methodology appears appropriate for all the loading configurations considered, except for loading configuration R2, for which conservative predictions are expected (and actually obtained) in terms of lifetime. A coupled elastic-plastic methodology would provide a more accurate physical description of the problem. However, such an approach would require complex and time-consuming computations, which may be unnecessary for engineering practical applications where a simple conservative design approach is required. In such a context, also the simulation of loading configuration R2 by employing the present methodology turns out to be appropriate, although a careful interpretation of the corresponding results is needed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the crack nucleation orientations of fretting-affected specimens made of AISI 1034 steel, subjected to cylindrical contact, and 35NCD16 steel alloy, subjected to both cylindrical and spherical contact, have been examined by means of an analytical methodology recently proposed by some of the present authors. Such a methodology is based on a closed-form solution for the stress/strain field determination within elastic bodies in contact, a multiaxial fatigue criterion for the fatigue assessment of the structural component, and a stress averaging method for the determination of the orientation of the critical plane.

Four different crack nucleation locations on the contact surface (starting to the contact trailing edge and moving toward the centre of the contact within the slip zone) have been alternatively taken into account to evaluate the influence of such a location on the crack nucleation orientation and lifetime.

The better estimations in terms of experimental crack paths are obtained when the crack nucleation location is considered at the centre of the slip zone, or at the point maximizing the Ruiz parameter within a fretting cycle. Moreover, this latter point together with the trailing edge are more representative of the actual crack nucleation location, experimentally found within the slip zone close to the edge of the contact.

Furthermore, it has been observed that as the crack nucleation location moves inward the contact region, the estimated number of loading cycles to failure generally increase. However, in the

present case no data related to the experimental number of loading cycles to failure are available for comparison.

Finally, it has been found that by assuming the point maximizing the Ruiz parameter as crack nucleation location, the best correlation between theoretical estimations and experimental evidences in terms of both crack nucleation location and orientation are obtained. Therefore, the point representing the crack nucleation location seems to be related to both the stress state within the component and the relative micro-slip between the bodies in contact.

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NOMENCLATURE

a	theoretical semi-width of the contact zone
c	theoretical semi-width of the stick zone
d	average grain size
E	Young modulus
m	slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed normal loading
m^*	slope of the S-N curve under fully reversed shear loading
$N_{eq,a}$	equivalent normal stress amplitude acting on the critical plane (assumed as fatigue parameter)
P	constant normal load applied to the pads
$Q(t)$	cyclic tangential load applied to the pads
Q_a	amplitude of the cyclic tangential load
R	pad radius
t	time
α_{cr}	critical plane orientation
α_{exp}	experimental crack path orientation
α_{th}	theoretical crack path orientation
μ	friction coefficient
ν	Poisson ratio
$\sigma_{af,-1}$	material fatigue strength under fully reversed normal loading, at a reference number N_0 of loading cycles
σ_B	axial bulk stress applied to the specimen
σ_u	ultimate tensile strength
σ_y	yield stress
$\tau_{af,-1}$	material fatigue strength under fully reversed shear loading, at a reference number N_0 of loading cycles

APPENDIX A

The theoretical aspects on which the analytical methodology presented in **Section 3** is based are outlined here. More in detail, the analytical solution to determine both stress and strain fields in contact problems subjected to fretting partial slip regime is firstly introduced [7,33,34]. Then, the main steps of the critical-plane based criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37], originally proposed for the plain fatigue assessment of metallic structures under multiaxial constant amplitude cyclic loading, are summarized. Finally, the Critical Direction Method (CDM) by Araujo et al. [38,39], implemented in the methodology to determine the critical plane orientation, is described.

A.1 Closed-form solution for elastic bodies in contact

The typical fretting testing configuration, where two pads (either cylindrical or spherical) are clamped against a flat specimen in partial slip regime, is schematized in **Figure A.1**. The reference frame $Oxyz$ is also shown in **Figure A.1**, as well as a normal constant force P and a cyclic tangential force $Q(t)$, applied to the pads. The contact problem between the specimen and each of the two pads may be studied as a contact between two elastically similar bodies [7,33].

Figure A.1.

As far as cylindrical contact problems are considered, the normal pressure distribution, $p(x)$, between the bodies is given by:

$$p(x) = \frac{2P}{\pi a^2} \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} \quad (\text{A. 1})$$

where the semi-width of the contact zone a can be expressed as follows:

$$a = \left(\frac{4PR}{\pi E^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{A. 2})$$

being R the relative radius of curvature of the two bodies in contact, and E^* the elastic modulus for plane strain condition.

Such a distribution, named Hertzian pressure distribution, is characterized by a parabolic shape with a maximum value for $x=0$, given by:

$$p_0 = \frac{2P}{\pi a} \quad (\text{A. 3})$$

As far as spherical contact problems are considered, the normal pressure distribution $p(r)$ (being $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$) between the bodies is given by:

$$p(r) = \frac{2P}{\pi a^2} \sqrt{a^2 - r^2} \quad (\text{A. 4})$$

where the semi-width of the contact zone a can be expressed as follows:

$$a = \left(\frac{3PR}{4E^*} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (\text{A. 5})$$

Such a distribution, named Hertzian pressure distribution, is characterized by a parabolic shape with a maximum value for $x=0$, given by:

$$p_0 = \frac{3P}{2\pi a^2} \quad (\text{A. 6})$$

Then, the components of the stress tensor in the vicinity of the contact zone, due to a constant normal load P , may be computed according to McEwen [34], for both cylindrical and spherical contact problems.

Now let us consider a constant tangential load Q , applied while maintaining constant the applied normal load P . The effect of the normal load and that of the tangential load may be independently examined and, subsequently, both stress and deformation fields for the two conditions may be combined together according to the superposition principle.

After the deformation, the contact zone is characterised by an inner region (named stick region) where no relative displacements arise between the bodies, and an outer region (named slip region) where relative displacements arise between the bodies. The stick region is characterised by a width equal to $2c$. Under such a condition, the relative displacement in the x-direction (that is, the relative slip, s , between two points lying on the contact surface) may be expressed as follows in case of cylindrical bodies:

$$s_x = - \left(\frac{1-\nu_1^2}{E_1} + \frac{1-\nu_2^2}{E_2} \right) \frac{\mu p_0}{a} x^2 \quad (\text{A. 7})$$

and in case of spherical bodies:

$$s_x = (2-\nu) \frac{3\mu P}{16Ga} \left[\left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \sin^{-1} \frac{c}{r}\right) \left(1 - 2 \frac{c^2}{r^2}\right) + \frac{2c}{\pi r} \left(1 - \frac{c^2}{r^2}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad \text{and} \quad s_y = 0 \quad (\text{A. 8})$$

where ν_1 , E_1 and ν_2 , E_2 are the Poisson coefficient and the elastic modulus of the two bodies in contact, respectively.

As far as cylindrical contact problems are considered, it can be determined the contact shear distribution $q(x)$:

$$q(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu p_0}{a} \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} & \text{for } c \leq |x| \leq a \\ \frac{\mu p_0}{a} \left(\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} - \sqrt{c^2 - x^2} \right) & \text{for } |x| < c \end{cases} \quad (\text{A. 9})$$

where the semi-width c of the stick region is:

$$c = a \left(1 - \frac{Q}{\mu P} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (\text{A. 10})$$

As far as spherical contact problems are considered, it can be determined the contact shear distribution $q(r)$:

$$q(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mu p_0}{a} \sqrt{a^2 - r^2} & \text{for } c \leq |r| \leq a \\ \frac{\mu p_0}{a} \left(\sqrt{a^2 - r^2} - \sqrt{c^2 - r^2} \right) & \text{for } |r| < c \end{cases} \quad (\text{A. 11})$$

where the semi-width c of the stick region is:

$$c = a \left(1 - \frac{Q}{\mu P} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (\text{A. 12})$$

Then, the components of the stress tensor in the vicinity of the contact zone, due to a tangential load Q , may be computed according to McEwen [34], for both cylindrical and spherical contact problems.

A.2 The Carpinteri et al. criterion

The main steps of the critical-plane based criterion, named Carpinteri et al. criterion [35-37], originally proposed for the plain fatigue assessment of metallic structures under multiaxial constant amplitude cyclic loading, are hereafter summarized.

According to the above criterion, the fatigue assessment of a structural component consists of two steps: the first one deals with the determination of the critical plane orientation, whereas the second one deals with the fatigue life evaluation carried out in such a plane. In more detail, the fatigue life evaluation is performed by employing an equivalent stress amplitude computed after the reduction of the multiaxial stress state to an equivalent uniaxial one.

Let us consider the stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t)$ in a generic point of a metallic body under cyclic loading. Both principal stresses $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ (with $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2 > \sigma_3$) and the corresponding principal directions 1,2,3 in such a point are generally time-varying. According to the Carpinteri et al. criterion, the averaged principal stress directions within a loading cycle can be identified, which are those corresponding to the time instant when σ_1 attains its maximum value within a loading cycle. Finally, the orientation of the critical plane is identified assuming the normal to such a plane to be rotated with respect to the averaged maximum principal stress direction by an angle which is a function of the material fatigue strengths $\sigma_{af,-1}$ and $\tau_{af,-1}$ under fully reversed normal and

shear loading, respectively (related to a reference number N_0 of loading cycles).

Once the orientation of the critical plane has been determined, the stress components acting on such a plane are computed. The normal stress component perpendicular to the critical plane is characterized by a fixed direction with respect to time and, consequently, both the mean value N_m and the amplitude N_a are easily determined. On the other hand, since the shear stress component lying on the critical plane has a time-varying direction, the amplitude C_a is uniquely computed by means of the Maximum Rectangular Hull method [28].

Finally, the number of loading cycles to failure, $N_{f,cal}$, may be determined by solving the following equation:

$$\sqrt{N_{eq,a}^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma'_{af,-1}}{\tau'_{af,-1}}\right)^2} C_a^2 = \sigma'_{af,-1} \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where $N_{eq,a}$ is the amplitude of the equivalent normal stress acting on the critical plane, given by:

$$N_{eq,a} = N_a + \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_m}{\sigma_u} \right) \quad (\text{A.14})$$

and $\sigma'_{af,-1}$ and $\tau'_{af,-1}$ are the finite life fatigue strengths for the finite fatigue life evaluation:

$$\sigma'_{af,-1} = \sigma_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_{f,cal}}{N_0} \right)^m \quad (\text{A.15a})$$

$$\tau'_{af,-1} = \tau_{af,-1} \left(\frac{N_{f,cal}}{N_0} \right)^{m^*} \quad (\text{A.15b})$$

being σ_u the ultimate tensile strength, and m and m^* the slopes of the S-N curves under fully reversed normal and shear loading, respectively.

A.3 The Critical Direction Method

The Critical Direction Method (CDM) proposed by Araujo et al. [38,39] is herein employed to determine the critical plane.

In a fretting testing configuration, the problem is typically two-dimensional, and therefore the critical plane is represented by a segment, with a given length l , starting from the hot-spot. The segment orientation α is defined by the angle between the segment and the line perpendicular to the surface of the structural component, starting from the hot-spot. Positive values of α are considered when the segment is towards the centre of the contact zone.

According to the CDM, a fatigue parameter is computed along each of the segments obtained by varying α in the range $-90^\circ \leq \alpha \leq +90^\circ$, with an angular increment equal to $\Delta\alpha$, that is, assuming each segment as a candidate to be the critical plane. The above fatigue parameter is a function of stress quantities, averaged along the segment. The orientation of the critical plane, α_{cr} , is determined by maximising such a parameter.

**INFLUENCE OF HOT-SPOT ON CRACK PATH AND LIFETIME ESTIMATION OF
FRETTING-AFFECTED STEEL COMPONENTS**

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Table 1. Mechanical and fatigue properties of AISI 1034 steel [42,44] and mechanical properties of chromium 52100 steel [42].

MATERIAL	E [GPa]	ν [-]	σ_u [MPa]	σ_y [MPa]	$\sigma_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	m [-]	$\tau_{af,-1}$ [MPa]	m^* [-]	N_0 [cycles]
AISI 1034 steel	200	0.3	600	350	299	-0.10	173	-0.10	$2 \cdot 10^6$
Chromium 52100 steel	210	0.3	-	1700	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 1. Fretting loading of: (a) experimental campaigns Nos 1 and 3, and (b) experimental campaign No. 2.

Table 2. Experimental campaign No. 1 [42]: fretting loading conditions.

Loading configuration	R [mm]	P [N/mm]	Q_a [N/mm]	a [mm]	c [mm]
R1	40	227	169	0.320	0.133
R2	40	540	282	0.494	0.320

Table 3. Mechanical and fatigue properties of 35NCD16 alloy steel [43,45] and mechanical properties of steel 100 C6 [43].

MATERIAL	E	ν	σ_u	σ_y	$\sigma_{af,-1}$	m	$\tau_{af,-1}$	m^*	N_0
	[GPa]	[-]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[-]	[MPa]	[-]	[cycles]
35NCD16 steel	200	0.3	1270	1127	361	-0.10	342	-0.07	$2 \cdot 10^6$
Steel 100 C6	195	0.3	-	1500	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4. Experimental campaign No. 2 [43]: fretting loading conditions.

Loading configuration	R	P	Q_a	σ_B	a	c
	[mm]	[N/mm]	[N/mm]	[MPa]	[mm]	[mm]
T1	80	1000	500	0	0.969	0.646
T2	80	1000	500	70	0.969	0.646
T3	80	1000	500	140	0.969	0.646
T4	80	1000	500	180	0.969	0.646
T5	80	1000	500	210	0.969	0.646

Table 5. Experimental campaign No. 3 [43]: fretting loading condition.

Loading configuration	R	P	Q_a	a	c
	[mm]	[N]	[N]	[mm]	[mm]
S1	200	5000	1300	1.905	1.700

Figure 2. Scheme for determining the critical plane orientation.

Figure 3. Different crack nucleation locations considered on the contact surface.

Figure 4. Fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, computed for the loading configuration R1 of experimental campaign No. 1, considering the hot-spot in: (a) point A, (b) point B, (c) point C, and (d) point D.

Figure 5. Fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, computed for the loading configuration R2 of experimental campaign No. 1, considering the hot-spot in: (a) point A, (b) point B, (c) point C, and (d) point D.

Figure 6. Fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, computed for the loading configurations T1-T5 of experimental campaign No. 2, considering the hot-spot in: (a) point A, (b) point B, (c) point C, and (d) point D.

Figure 7. Fatigue parameter, $N_{eq,a}(\alpha)$, computed for the loading configurations S1 of the experimental campaign No. 3, considering the hot-spot in: (a) point A, (b) point B, (c) point C, and (d) point D.

Table 6. Crack path orientation estimated by considering the hot-spot in points A, B, C, or D, for each loading configuration of the experimental campaigns examined.

Experimental campaign No.	Loading configuration	$\alpha_{th,A}$ [°]	$\alpha_{th,B}$ [°]	$\alpha_{th,C}$ [°]	$\alpha_{th,D}$ [°]
1	R1	9.0	14.0	23.0	46.0
	R2	9.0	15.0	21.0	46.0
2	T1	5.0	17.0	23.0	43.0
	T2	5.0	16.0	22.0	46.0
	T3	5.0	16.0	22.0	45.0
	T4	5.0	15.0	21.0	38.0
	T5	5.0	15.0	21.0	37.0
3	S1	1.0	18.0	29.0	76.0

Figure 8. Crack path orientation experimentally observed [42,43] and theoretical ones estimated by considering the hot-spot in point A, B, C or D, for the loading configurations: (a) R2, (b) T2, and (c) S1.

Figure 9. Number of loading cycles to failure evaluated by employing point A, B, C, or D as the hot-spot for each test examined.

Figure A.1. Typical cylinder/spherical-to-flat fretting fatigue test, under both constant normal force P and cyclic tangential force $Q(t)$.